

THE PROCESS ANALYSIS OF STACKING WORKER IN AUTOCLAVE ACTION, ANALYSIS AND EVALUATION OF DYNAMIC CHARACTERISTICS

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ABSTRACT

The way of stacking in autoclave is based on hand lay-up with manual labor. This makes quality control difficult. In this study, we aim to establish criteria and standardize the work process of this method. This paper discusses how differences in the hand lay-up work process and workers' skill level influence the mechanical performance of molded products. Carbon cloth prepreg was stacked in three layers in the mold. The fiber orientation of the carbon cloth was set using one edge of the mold as the plane of reference. The first layer was 0°, the second was 45°, and the third was 90°. To achieve this, the mold required the application of the hand lay-up method. Subjects were allowed to choose their process and molding tools. Subject A had 13 years, and subject B had 1 year of professional experience. The requirements are calculated higher than the appearance, which allows us to verify the significant mechanical properties between expert workers and beginner workers clearly. Under the

condition where the requirement and purpose were defined as the molding requirements, we clarified many differences in use of tools, posture, in addition working time, the way of process between subjects. For the automation robots of mass production, we will study the basic concept how to avoid the negative influences which are likely to occur on flat surface, corner R, and edges. Moreover, we continue to examine how different years of experience exert the influence to molding performance produced by hand lay-up method.

1 INTRODUCTION

In aeronautic and automobile manufacture, the incorporation of CFRP in three-dimensional parts has increased significantly in recent years. The way of stacking in autoclave is based on hand lay-up with manual labor. In aircraft field, it changes over to mass production by automatic stacking. Use of manual labor makes quality control difficult, as this has a large influence on the mechanical properties, such as the accuracy and strength, of parts that are produced. There are no reports of the way and where to cut prepreg sheets, and the way to stack prepreg sheets in stacking process, the way to vacuum in bagging process. The way to vacuum influences the performance of thickness and irregularity of the corner shape. There is also no reports of the vacuum process influences the twist of fiber and the area to cut, wrinkles on a surface and relative roughness of flat surface. In this study, we aim to establish criteria and standardize the work process of this method. This paper discusses how differences in the hand lay-up work process and workers' skill level influence the mechanical performance of molded products.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

As shown in Fig. 1, the material of mold is calcium silicate. Coefficient of thermal expansion of calcium silicate is extremely low, because it is important to have excellent dimensional stability. Mold release treatment is already done on surface of the mold with epoxy resin, to have smoothness. We prepared three molds. We used a tray-shaped square mold measuring 405mm on each side with an edge height of 30mm.

Figure 1: Mold

2.1 Experimental Materials

We used carbon fiber T-300 3K plain woven fabric epoxy prepreg sheet (produced by Toho Tenax Co., Ltd.) as the reinforcing material.

2.2 Experimental Method

The stacking experiment was proceeded in the cleaning room. The minimum required value of temperature, humidity, and mist in the cleaning room was class 100,000, $23^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$, under 65%. Carbon cloth prepreg was stacked in three layers in the above mold. The fiber orientation of the carbon cloth was set using one edge of the mold as the plane of reference. The first layer was 0° , the second was 45° , and the third was 90° . To achieve this, the mold required the application of the hand lay-up method. Subjects were allowed to choose their process and molding tools. Subject A had 13 years, and subject B had 1 year of professional experience respectively.

Figure 2: Stacking Experiment

As shown in Table.1, we clarify the basic process of hand lay-up work, and show the design guideline of work process. We also clarified the differences of work process influence the accuracy of form and dynamic characteristics of molding. According to Fig.2, required materials and tools of hand lay-up process were prepared within each subject's reach, and recorded by video camera. We verified the stacking movement and process analysis (Table 1) with the video.

	Requirements and Purpose
Process Analysis	Comparison of work time
	Use of tools
	Comparison of work posture
Analysis of Physical Property	Difference of product form
	Analysis of the section
	Dynamic characteristic

Table 1: Evaluation Method of Process Analysis

2.3 Molding Method

As shown in Fig. 2, while the expert, subject A's, movements were very smooth, subject B's motions were very awkward. When considering working posture, subject B's body was tilted forward, his head was positioned closer to the mold than subject A. As for using the tools and their fingers, subject A was precise, but subject B repeated many actions and often checked his work. It also took him a long time to complete the process because he did not use one single method.

Figure 3: Comparative Analysis of Stacking Time

2.4 Analysis of Molding and Detail of Work Time

As shown in Fig.3, we compare and analyze the molding time, subject A works without wasted movements with a good posture and well balanced fingers, he focus on his work and uses the right tools for the rights places. Speedy movements of fingers for the next process reduce work time. Subject B spent time for stacking about twice more than subject A, but the time for bagging process is about half. So it is clear there is big difference in experience level of each subject, the time for bagging and stacking.

Figure 4: Molding Bottom Face Pictures of Subject A and B

As shown in Fig.4, after molding, we peeled the bagging film, molding of subject B has wrinkles all over. On the other hand, molding of subject A has hardly wrinkles all over. Therefore we make a pulling test to verify the influence of dynamic characteristic by wrinkles. Moreover, as shown in Fig.4, we clarify the difference of the stacking requirement's level by analysis of the cross section observing.

Figure 5: Comparison of Time for Using Tools

2.5 Time Spent Usage of Tools and Process Analysis

As shown in Fig. 5, we analyzed the use of tools required for laminated work. Subject A uses the cutter more frequently than the scissors when cutting off excess materials in the stacking process. On the other hand, subject B uses the scissors and the cutter alternately, but confirm it each time. When using the plastic paint knife, subject B repeated many actions and used the plastic paint knife 1.5 times more than subject A. Furthermore, subject B uses the knife made of metal for stacking process. He uses the plastic paint knife made of bamboo for bagging process. Subject A and subject B both used tools properly. However, there was a difference in time spent using these tools because the experienced subject used his tools in an experienced sliding motion and subjects varied in their strength when pressing down with tools. This shows that the experience and proficiency level affects time usage. We will perform analysis to have an influence on the dynamic characteristic by a pressure measurement in future.

Figure 6: Analysis of Critical Path

As shown in Fig.6, we analyze subject A needs short time for each process. On the other hand, subject B takes time twice as long to work for each process than subject A. Based on this, we make an interview with each subject through the video verification. As shown in Table 2, process analysis table, we disclosed the answers of interview from each subject. Subject A can make quick judgments because subject A has 13 years of professional experience. In addition, subject A is used to working quickly. Subject A can work uniformly and rhythmically by using the right tools for the right place. Subject A thinks ahead to the next process. Subject A gave confident answers to questions about process. On the other hand, subject B is in the middle of acquiring skills by watching and copying the movements of subject A. As a result, subject B doesn't assimilate a relationship between materials and tools to work quickly and correctly. Subject B responded to interview questions by watching the footage and reflecting on his process. Subject B is uncertain of how to use his fingers. Therefore subject B makes many unnecessary movements. Subject B's answers to interview questions were unclear and non-specific. In subject B's case, his process largely depends on intuition. Subject B wastes prepreg by cutting and rolling out more than necessary. We disclosed the specifically influence for physical property by verifying the video.

Process	Subject A	Subject B
Positioning the Release Film	Put it into the mold without making wrinkles	Put it into the mold while making wrinkles
Arranging the Breather Cloth (Securing)	Turned the mold upside down and pushed the breather down	Set the breather from the stacking surface's position
Placing Inside the Bagging Film	Placed the mold in the film and quickly closed it with tape	Repeatedly made wrinkles in both sides numerous times before
Vacuum Drawing	Checked whether it was okay after pulling 5 times and checking once	Pulled it 4 times, pulled it back 3 times
Checking for Leaks	Carefully checked places which appear at risk of having problems	Repeated the task in all of the corners
Process Comparison	Sensed with his fingertips and tools and applied the square scale	Often made checks and repeated actions; attitude for not being able
Working Time Comparison	Did not unnecessarily repeat tasks	Was overly conscious and often repeated tasks
Use of Tools	Used only when needed; used the chisel on a wide number of	Divided the application of strength into three steps; use of
Comparing Even Part Stacking	Repeated the tasks on each side	Repeated the tasks on each side
Comparing Corner Part Stacking	Put it in by sensing with his fingertips and with the pressure	Uneven application of strength and unnecessary repetition of
Working Posture Comparison	Had no shakiness in his stance	Had his neck bent at 90° which looked painful; was confused as

Table 2: process Analysis Table

2.6 Type of Test Piece and Evaluation Method

For clarifying the dynamic characteristics of each subject, we cut the moldings and we observe the cross section of moldings and make a pulling test. As shown in Fig.7, we cut out 30mm×200mm rectangle test piece from the bottom face, then made a pulling test. We also cut out 30 mm×30mm from the corner R, and analyzed between layers by watching the cross section of the corner R.

Figure 7: Cutting Test Part

We clarified the basic process of hand lay-up of Table 1 and showed the design guideline of work process. Therefore based on the result of Table 1, we disclosed the difference of the work process influence for form accuracy of molding and dynamic characteristic. As shown in Fig.8, the result of subject A is close to designed value in high modulus. About subject B's result, with visual observation, we couldn't see clear differences between subject A and subject B's moldings. But this time, the result of test showed the clear differences by experience. The influence of bottom face wrinkles is hardly any difference as shown in Fig.8 than the visual observation in Fig.4.

Modulus

(a) Subject A

(b) Subject B

Tensile Strength

(c) Subject A

(d) Subject B

Figure 8: Pull Test Results

Based on the result of pulling test, as shown in Table 3, there is no significant difference of elastic modulus, on the flat surface there is no difference because of experience. Working hours and uneven work are depends on each subject. In this study, I couldn't find any surface irregularity.

Tensile strength and other

sample name	Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Thickness (mm)	width (mm)
SubjectA1	46.12898	530.62573	0.73	25.075
SubjectA2	44.65313	494.98129	0.728	25.082
SubjectA3	46.43985	542.15509	0.732	25.071
SubjectA4	42.29863	488.38998	0.733	25.073
SubjectB1	40.54572	478.75378	0.729	25.076
SubjectB2	38.0998	442.7254	0.789	25.068
SubjectB3	41.09168	411.95233	0.77	25.057
SubjectB4	41.44781	526.58905	0.709	25.074
Ave.	42.45021	492.92951	0.73575	25.0765

Table 3: Result of Pulling Test Analysis

2.7 Analysis of Corner Part and Evaluation Method

In this study, the number of stacking is only three layers. But the cut of wrinkles in the corner R and the way being piled up, the way of bagging with secondary material after stacking process, the order of workers, and all materials are folded in the corner, it makes significant difference in the corner. We verify detailed information by analysis.

(a) Subject A (b) Subject B (c) Design Requirement

Figure 9: Analysis Results and Cross-Sectional Observation of Corner (R)

As shown in Fig.9, we were able to verify thickness of corner R, wrinkles, fiber disorder, and gaps among cloth depending on each subject. On the cross-sectional observation of deep edges, the different years' of experience gives fine density of the cross-section results by gaining experiences. The deep gap was observed on subject B's cross-sectional result. This result was occurred by bagging sheets folding up in the middle of layered cross-section in vacuuming process. This wrinkle has a possibility to incur a decline of dynamic characteristic. In addition, the product thickness on the bottom was extremely thin than vertical surface on the images of subject B. Compare to the result of cross-sectional analysis on the subject A's molded object, it was clear that it has even thickness and less gaps among fibers regarding corner R.

2.8 Analysis of Wrinkle Influence and Evaluation Method

In this study, there are a lot of plain surface due to bottom surface, corner R and vertical surface. So it is possible to minimize wrinkles with comparative ease. By visual observation, we analyze products of each subject.

(a) Subject A (b) Subject B (c) Design Requirement

Figure 10: Cross Section Observation of Wrinkles and Design Requirement

As shown in Fig.10, the wrinkles on bagging side with visual observation are luster by being piled up secondary materials. So as shown in Fig.10, we found that the wrinkles doesn't influence. There are some voids and resin layers around wrinkles in the middle of the picture of subject A. but it became clear that it doesn't affect design requirements such as tensile or compression, and the strength is higher than subject B's cross section. And subject B' cross section with many wrinkle's influence for dynamic characteristic is low by molding smoothly.

3 EXPERIMENT RESULT AND CONSIDERATION

The mold used in this study has three major elements; flat smoothness, corner R and four corners with deep edges. Thus, the requirements are calculated higher than the appearance, which allows us to verify the significant mechanical properties between expert worker and beginner workers clearly. As shown in the test result, we clarified influence of wrinkle by bagging and board thickness by vacuum. We also examined the cause of occurrence of convex-shaped twisted fiber at the corner of wrinkles, and the influence to strength caused by resin. But about smooth part, there is hardly any difference.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Under the condition where the requirement and purpose were defined as the molding requirements, we clarified many differences in use of tools, posture, in addition working time, the way of process between subjects. We also established the standard process of hand lay-up with prepreg sheets. In the future study, we are considering to verify the cases of plural pieces of layers, or different kind of fiber and resin. And it is also needed to examine the characteristics of structural parts and materials. Since we didn't examine anything about wrinkles this time, it is necessary to analyze pipe shape part or the parts where twisted fiber or wrinkles are likely to occur due to unevenness shape. Therefore, for the automation robots of mass production, we will study the basic concept how to avoid the negative influences which are likely to occur on flat surface, corner R, and edges. Moreover, we continue to examine how different years of experience exert the influence to molding performance produced by hand lay-up method.

REFERENCES

- [1] Z. Maekawa, H. Hamada, S. Ishibashi, *Society of Materials Science* 38, 140-142, 1989-05-23
- [2] A. Nagasaka, Y. Taketaba, T. Suwa, *Memoirs of Nagano National College of Technology* 47, 2-2, 2013-06-30
- [3] M. Iida, K. Sakai, Y. Suzuki, Y. Suzuki, *JSME annual meeting* 2010(4), 205-206, 2010-09-04
- [4] H. Maki, Y. Yasui, *Kobunshi Kagaku*, Vol.28, No.319, pp.888-892, Nov.,1971
- [5] Y. Tani, T. Kikuti, A. Otani, *M&P* 21, 5p, 2013-11-08
- [6] Y. Nishikawa & 4 others, *Materials*, 54, 494-499
- [7] Y. Hirano, H. Kusano, Y. Aoki, *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, 40(2014),153-159